

Advances in Pile Oscillation Technique in Fast and Thermal Reactors

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ABSTRACT

The pile oscillation technique is an ideal method for measuring small sample reactivity worth with sub-tenth-pcm precision. In this work, we review the principles of the technique, its data analysis and modeling approaches. We compare its implementations in thermal and fast neutron spectra with emphasis on differences in global and local signal perturbations caused by an oscillating sample and we discuss the choice of detectors needed to separate individual reaction channels. Then we present the design and initial performance of a new versatile pile oscillator at the fast, zero-power VENUS-F reactor, which has demonstrated stable operation, outstanding consistency between ten detectors and excellent experimental uncertainty of 0.03 pcm during oscillations of a B₄C sample (worth \approx 6 pcm). Ongoing experimental program is dedicated to oscillations of structural materials (Cr, Ni, Fe, SS). In future, oscillations of actinides, lead and other materials directly supporting nuclear data needs for lead cooled fast reactors are foreseen. Forthcoming upgrades of the VENUS-F pile oscillator target Doppler effect measurements through oscillations of heated samples and implementation of hybrid (local + global) detection in fast spectra.

Keywords: pile oscillation technique, reactivity worth measurement, flux perturbation, fast and thermal neutron spectra, VENUS-F

1. INTRODUCTION

Pile oscillation technique is currently experiencing a great renewal of interest in research reactor laboratories in Europe and North America. It has been 80 years since Wigner [1] introduced the pile oscillator as “an instrument which causes periodic variations of the neutron intensity in a pile of critical or smaller than critical size.” Significant historical implementations include oscillators in thermal reactor such as MINERVE [2], [11], [24], AGN-201 [13], PROTEUS [26], in fast-thermal coupled facilities SEG [22], STEK [23], and in fast reactors such as the ZPPR [25], BFS-1 [21]. After several decades of limited activity, pile oscillators have recently re-emerged in both thermal and fast reactors, particularly through ongoing programs at CROCUS [14][15][17], AKR-2 [28] and VENUS-F [7]-[10], where modern detectors, data acquisition systems and advanced analysis methods are being applied. Future pile oscillators are being prepared at the LR-0 reactor at CVR and in glory holes of Godiva-IV and Flattop assemblies at NCERC [27].

In practice, a pile oscillator is a mechanical device that periodically moves a sample between low-flux and high-flux regions of a reactor core. This motion causes reactivity perturbations that in turn cause neutron flux variations, which are detected and used to reconstruct the reactivity evolution. Pile oscillation measurements are performed primarily to investigate sample properties. The fundamental measurement of the sample reactivity worth can be used for determination of other quantities, for

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example integral cross sections [2], capture-to-fission ratios [3], and resonance integrals [4]. Such studies aim at validation of nuclear data and transport codes.

Another purpose of pile oscillation measurements is to study reactor kinetics by analyzing the relationship between the neutron flux response in the frequency domain and a periodic reactivity input, known as the reactor transfer function [5]. This dynamic measurement does not require prior knowledge of the sample reactivity worth and it relies on the relative amplitude and phase shift between the sample motion and the neutron flux evolution.

As the basics of the oscillation technique have been extensively described elsewhere [6], this paper starts with a concise summary of the principles (Section 2). We then focus on comparison of pile oscillator implementations in fast and thermal reactors (Section 4) and description of a pile oscillator development currently ongoing in the fast VENUS-F reactor (Section 5) at the Belgian nuclear research centre SCK CEN [7]-[10]. A detailed description of the design prepared for a forthcoming plutonium oscillation experiment at VENUS-F is provided in the PHYSOR 2026 contribution by F. Di Croce [10], which is complementary to this work.

2. PILE OSCILLATION TECHNIQUE

Pile oscillators differ in their design and operational details, which are tailored to a specific reactor type, spectral range, and experimental objective. All rely on a common principle: a periodic movement of a small sample (small in reactivity worth, typically several pcm) within a reactor core, causing periodic neutron flux perturbations, which are measured and analyzed to determine the sample reactivity worth. Pile oscillation experiments are practically always performed in critical systems. The possibility to carry out a pile oscillation experiment in a sub-critical system (which is less costly to construct, license, and operate) driven by an external neutron source was also investigated, however, it was concluded that it is difficult to obtain small sample reactivity worth in a sub-critical pile [12]. Pile oscillation techniques can be classified according to three main parameters: oscillating sample motion, power compensation system (i.e., stable power or not), and type of measured perturbation (local, global).

2.1. Oscillating sample motion

For the reactivity worth measurements, the detector signal measured during the dwell time (sample in a static position) is of interest, therefore, the sample usually moves axially (into and out of the core) with a pseudo-square (trapezoidal) waveform [2,7,10,11] that minimizes the transition time.

An alternative option to the sample full extraction from the core is utilization of a neutron trap inside the fuel zone. In a thermal neutron flux, if a sample is placed inside a Cd box, it is practically invisible for the neutron flux. If such a sample is extracted from the Cd box, its reactivity worth can be measured without the need of a movement from the fuel zone outside of the reactor, which is especially advantageous in large reactors as in BR1, where such an experiment was carried out to measure the reactor transfer function [19].

For the transfer function measurement [5], a sinusoidal sample motion is preferred as it contains only one frequency, while the square wave oscillation excites many frequencies in the reactor (ideally, the flux amplitude should have sinusoidal shape). Another possibility is rotational motion, which offers an easy way to reach sinusoidal waveform and it enables oscillations at higher frequencies. Oscillator rods designated for rotation are designed asymmetrically over the rotating axis [16] as to produce unevenness in the reactivity and, therefore, they do not operate in the centre of the reactor core.

2.2. Local and global signal

The standard detector location is sufficiently far from the oscillating sample in order to measure the global effect of the oscillations. Using the global signal, the reactivity evolution can be determined, which reflects the combined effects of scattering and absorption in the sample. Under specific experimental conditions, it is possible to isolate the effect of a certain reaction channel. Oscillating a non-fissile sample in a region with a flat neutron flux (minimal gradient), scattering effects are

suppressed, enabling measurement of the capture component. Oscillation in a region with steep neutron flux gradient enhances the scattering contribution.

In case detectors are positioned far and near the oscillating sample, the setup is called a hybrid pile oscillator [2,10]. The global detector measures the reactivity variations, while the local detector measures the reactivity variations and the local neutron flux perturbations. Thanks to the simultaneous measurement of local and global signals, hybrid pile oscillator enables reaching beyond simple reactivity effect measurement by experimentally disentangling opposite effects of fission vs. capture and scattering vs. capture. Significantly different implementation of a hybrid pile oscillator is needed in thermal and fast systems, see Section 3.

For local perturbation measurement, the choice of the detectors and their geometry towards the oscillating sample are crucial. A fission chamber with a deposit that would surround the oscillation channel is considered to be the best option, however, manufacturing such detectors is extremely challenging. The usual solution is to surround the oscillation channel with multiple miniature detectors minimizing the sample-detector distance [2,11,14,15] because the local perturbation rapidly decreases with distance. A novel alternative has been proposed at VENUS-F, see Section 4.

2.3. Open and closed loop

If, during the oscillations, the reactor power is kept stable by compensation using a calibrated autopilot rod (based on the global signal measurement), the pile oscillation is said to be performed in a closed loop. The sample reactivity worth equals the worth of the rod movement. As the detector count rates are constant during closed loop oscillations, such experiments are insensitive to detector dead time.

If the reactor power freely evolves during oscillations, the experiment is said to be performed in an open loop. The global signal is recorded continuously during the oscillations while the reactor state oscillates. The oscillations can be between sub-critical and super-critical state, critical and super-critical state, or critical and sub-critical state. The former was shown to be superior as it enables limiting the power drift [7].

The equivalence of the open and closed loop techniques concerning measurement uncertainties was proven several times [10,11]. A fundamental lower bound on the pile oscillation technique precision is the reactor noise (i.e. intrinsic stochastic fluctuations of the neutron population).

2.4. Pile oscillation advantages and limitations

Let's consider the two approaches to the small sample reactivity worth measurement: the pile oscillation technique and a null-reactivity method (i.e. a simple difference of two static measurements with control rod position adjusted to keep the reactor critical with sample inserted and extracted). A classical book on small-sample reactivity measurements by Foell [6] states that "the ac amplification is the main advantage of the oscillation method" (p. 42). This was relevant in the time of the book release (1972) but it is obsolete nowadays. Although the two approaches are equivalent in principle, we find the pile oscillation method superior for the following reasons.

During a static measurement it may be difficult to keep the critical control rod height stable for a long time. Due to temperature effects and possible other disturbances, it is usually necessary to keep adjusting the critical control rod height during the static measurement. Such adjustments may be of the order of the small reactivity effect of the measured sample (~ 1 mm of the control rod height at VENUS-F), thus hindering the effect. Temperature and other effects (e.g. detector gain instability) are slow compared to the typical range of oscillation frequency (~ 0.01–0.1 Hz).

Moreover, as the reactor shutdown for sample loading is required between the two static measurements, the precision of the null-reactivity method is limited by the precision to what the reactor criticality is known. If the criticality cannot be reproduced better than the uncertainty of the pile oscillation experiment, which is practically always the case, the pile oscillation technique is clearly superior.

The precision of the sample position may be under question if the sample is inserted only once for a long static measurement. Pile oscillation technique allows for many sample insertions, which can average out accidental misalignments.

Pile oscillation techniques allow to accurately measure very small reactivity worth (a few pcm) with exceptional precision (tenths of pcm), which enables measurements even in cases when only small amount of material is available. Beyond that, it helps to reduce the impact of the reactivity worth experiment on the reactor geometry. That is relevant in cases (especially important in fast reactors) where large amounts of material would be needed to ensure sufficiently large reactivity worth for reliable measurements using a null-reactivity method.

Pile oscillation technique is limited to measurements of small reactivity worth, when point kinetics assumptions hold. Another practical limitation is that when the oscillating sample cannot be taken completely out of the system and it remains in the vicinity of the reactor, where it is assumed to cause zero reactivity effect, while it contributes to the “background”, ideally causing a reactivity effect smaller than the experimental uncertainty. It is an advantage of a null-reactivity method, which enables removal of the sample not only from the reactor core but even from the reactor hall.

2.5. Pile oscillation setup

Pile oscillator is a complex device and a complete oscillation setup typically includes the following components: an oscillation assembly consisting of a channel to accommodate the sample and a channel for local detector(s), the oscillating sample mounted in a holder, a drive element (a rigid rod to attach the sample or a suspension thread that minimizes neutron perturbation [16]), a linear motor or rotating drive system with its controller for sample movement, detectors with electronic chains and DAQ system (capable of recording synchronized detector signals and the sample position, if the data are to be analyzed in the frequency domain, see Section 2.6), a calibrated compensation mechanism and its controller (in case of a closed loop oscillation).

2.6. Data analysis

The measured data can be analyzed in two ways, both under the assumption that the detector signals satisfy the point kinetics approximation [7]: in time or frequency domain. The choice between them depends on the oscillation waveform, signal quality and experimental objectives.

In the time domain, the global detector signal is processed using the inverse point kinetics equation, which outputs the reactivity as a function of the measured neutron flux time evolution. It requires the knowledge of the reactor kinetic parameters (effective delayed neutron fraction, prompt neutron generation time, and delayed neutron group data). This method provides a full reactivity evolution during oscillation that can be directly compared with the sample motion.

In the frequency domain, the detector signal and the sample position are processed using the Fourier transform. The ratio of their fundamental harmonic components gives the oscillation amplitude, from which the sample reactivity worth can be obtained using the Zero Power Transfer Function, which is (for small amplitude fluctuations of reactivity) the expression of point kinetics in the frequency domain and as such also depends on the reactor kinetic parameters. As the sample position is not linearly related to reactivity, this simple analysis is applicable only in case of a square sample motion with negligible transition time. For trapezoidal or sinusoidal motion, the reactivity shape needs to be known.

For hybrid pile oscillators [2],[11], the data analysis does not simply use the global signal to retrieve reactivity and combine it with local flux. Instead, by synchronizing the acquisition of the local and global signals, the different sensitivity of global and local perturbations to certain reaction channels can be investigated, see Section 3. In practice this can be implemented by constructing a phase space of the local and global signals. Different neutron reactions induce distinct slopes in this phase space.

2.7. Modeling

Modelling small sample reactivity worth in stochastic simulations is challenging. The precision of the classical eigenvalue difference method (i.e. difference between two criticality calculations with and without the sample) is limited because subtracting two nearly identical values leads to large relative uncertainty. For a typical high-fidelity reactor geometry model, billions of neutron histories need to be simulated to reach a standard error of 1 pcm, resulting in 1.4 pcm uncertainty in the calculated reactivity

worth. For example, in case of a sample worth of 7 pcm this corresponds to 20% uncertainty, see Table I. A reasonable uncertainty would be 10x smaller, which would require 100x longer calculations, which is not feasible.

Another option is to use perturbation theory. Modern Monte Carlo transport codes (e.g., MCNP, Serpent, OpenMC) include built-in first-order perturbation estimators (e.g., PERT, KPERT, GPT, XGPT), which provide better precision than the eigenvalue difference method, see Table I for illustration of the variability and limitations of different Monte Carlo approaches for predicting a small reactivity effect. However, their accuracy is limited to specific cases [9] (weakly scattering samples, fast neutron systems). Exact perturbation methods exist only in custom versions of Monte Carlo implementations [20], but are not available in standard code versions. A promising development is the Black Body Exact Perturbation method [29], which enables exact perturbation calculations without any internal code modifications.

Table I. Reactivity worth of a B4C sample (oscillated at VENUS-F [7], see Section 4) calculated with various Monte Carlo codes, nuclear data libraries and calculation methods (EVDM - eigenvalue difference method, XGPT - eXtended Generalized Perturbation Theory module in Serpent, KPERT - first-order perturbation theory estimator for k_{eff} in MCNP).

Code	Method	Library	$\Delta\rho$ [pcm]	abs.err. [pcm]
Serpent2	EVDM	JEFF-3.3	-6.0	1.2
Serpent2	XGPT	JEFF-3.3	-6.8	0.3
MCNP6.3	EVDM	JEFF-3.1.2	-7.9	1.4
MCNP6.3	KPERT	JEFF-3.1.2	-6.7	0.8
MCNP6.3	KPERT	JENDL-4.0	-7.9	0.8
MCNP6.3	KPERT	ENDF/B-VIII.0	-6.4	0.8

A practical alternative for feasibility studies and experiment design (although not for accurate small reactivity worth calculation) is to artificially increase the sample density in the model. This increases the magnitude of the sample reactivity worth and improves the relative error. Results from a set of such calculations with several higher densities can be extrapolated to estimate the reactivity worth of a real sample (taking into account possible neutron self-shielding).

Deterministic neutron transport solvers (e.g., ERANOS, APOLLO3, DRAGON) give numerically exact reactivity worth values, however, the result accuracy depends on energy, spatial, and angular discretization, homogenization methods etc. Moreover, a small reactivity worth does not necessarily imply a small local perturbation. If a sample is highly absorbing or scattering, the induced local flux gradient can be steep and refined resolution in modeling is needed.

3. IMPLEMENTATIONS IN FAST VS THERMAL REACTORS

Although the underlying concept is the same, the implementation of pile oscillation technique differs between fast and thermal systems. In thermal reactors reactivity perturbations are dominated by absorption and scattering with large thermal cross sections and strong, narrow resonances in the epithermal range, which produce large flux perturbations. Even very small samples (~0.1 g) can cause reactivity effects of ~ 10 pcm [24].

In fast reactors, perturbations arise mainly from scattering and absorption in the fast energy range, where cross sections are smaller and vary less with energy, and remain localized, making the local signal weaker and more sensitive to detector placement. Larger sample masses are required to achieve measurable reactivity worth but excessively large samples should be avoided to prevent different spectral conditions in different parts of the sample.

In thermal reactors, a perturbation caused by an oscillating sample spreads over a wider region (e.g. in the CROCUS reactor, the local flux perturbation vanishes at a distance of 15 cm [15]) than in fast reactors. This is not due to the neutron mean free path but due to the neutron slowing-down process, which propagates perturbations over large regions in thermal-spectrum reactors. Fission neutrons undergo multiple scattering events in the moderator (and diffuse) across a wide region. Any local change in

absorption or scattering modifies the slowing down density and causes thermal flux changes over a broad region. As a result, the reactivity perturbation is redistributed through the entire moderation chain. In fast reactors, moderation is almost absent as scattering on heavy nuclei causes only minimal energy loss per collision. The neutron spectrum is dominated by forward scattering with limited spatial redistribution, therefore, perturbation remains localized.

The global signal reflects the combined effect of all reaction processes in the oscillating sample on neutron economy of the entire system, thus almost any neutron detector can measure global signal. The local signal reflects the reactivity variations as well as the changes in the local flux shape and spectral effects caused by the oscillating sample. Therefore, the type of the local detector is important. As different reactions affect local and global signals differently, combining both signals makes it possible to separate contributions from different processes, see Table II.

In thermal spectrum oscillators, only thermal neutron detectors are used. The separation between scattering and fission in the sample is based on the fact that scattering increases both global and local signals, while fission increases the global signal but decreases the local one (typically measured with ²³⁵U fission chambers) [2], [11]. The situation is different in fast spectrum because fission in the sample increases both the global and local signals in ²³⁵U fission chambers. We propose using threshold detectors (e.g. ²³⁸U fission chambers) as local detectors because scattering in the sample is expected to increase the global signal but decrease the local one. However, this approach has yet to be confirmed experimentally and it is likely to depend strongly on the characteristics of the reactor system.

Table II. The increase (↑) and decrease (↓) in the global and local signal detected with ²³⁵U and ²³⁸U fission chambers (FC) caused by the three possible reaction channels in an oscillating sample in a typical thermal and fast system.

Spectrum	Signal	Capture	Capture	Scattering	Scattering	Fission	Fission
		²³⁵ U FC	²³⁸ U FC	²³⁵ U FC	²³⁸ U FC	²³⁵ U FC	²³⁸ U FC
Thermal	Global	↓		↑		↑	
	Local	↓		↑		↓	
Fast	Global	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Local	↓	↓	↑	↓	↑	↑

In thermal reactors, sample reactivity worth is often obtained by comparison with reference materials that are used to calibrate the measurement process and eliminate the dependence on the kinetic parameters, so improving the measurement accuracy. An optimal reference sample has very well known cross sections for all neutron interactions in the energy range of interest and similar sensitivity to reaction channels as the material under investigation (e.g., an oscillating sample with a dominating capture channel would ideally require a reference sample with dominating capture channel as well). Common reference samples in thermal spectrum oscillators are gold, lithium, boron etc. [11]. Reference samples have not been used yet in fast spectrum oscillation experiments because it is not easy to find materials that have accurately known cross sections of all relevant reactions channels in the fast energy range.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF THE VENUS-F OSCILLATOR

VENUS-F is a fast, zero-power reactor [18] that serves as a mockup of heavy-liquid metal-cooled reactor designs. Since 2025 a new pile oscillator [7-10] has been under construction at VENUS-F. Its design features and future development perspectives are discussed in this section. Unlike usual arrangements that oscillate samples all of the same geometry (sometimes using an automatic sample changer) in the same neutron field, the VENUS-F pile oscillator aims to be a versatile device capable of oscillating samples of various sizes in various neutron spectral conditions. This brings technical challenges and requires tailored experimental approach.

To achieve this versatility, several oscillation assemblies of different designs have been manufactured, which can accommodate samples with diameters up to 42 mm (and a potential to reach up to 70 mm).

The neutron spectrum can be fine-tuned to the desired fast or epithermal energy range thanks to the materials surrounding the oscillation channel and the possibility to load the oscillation assembly at various locations in the VENUS-F core lattice. Dedicated sample holders are manufactured for each sample.

The first version of the VENUS-F pile oscillator operates in open loop mode with a dwell time of 15-60 s, a transition time of 27 s, and global signal measurement using ten ^{235}U fission chambers placed in the reflector. Its performance has been thoroughly validated using a B_4C sample (worth ≈ 7 pcm, see Table I) showing an excellent agreement among all detectors [7]. An experimental uncertainty of 0.03 pcm has been reached, which is comparable to measurement uncertainties observed in MINERVE (0.01 to 0.03 pcm [24]) and CROCUS (0.04 pcm [15]). The first application of the VENUS-F oscillator is an ongoing campaign in collaboration with EPFL to oscillate structural materials (Fe, Ni, Cr, SS) that were recently oscillated in thermal spectra in CROCUS [15].

Future oscillation experiments at VENUS-F (planned for 2026 and beyond) will target samples such as Pu, U, Pb etc., chosen due to known deficiencies in nuclear data relevant for lead-cooled fast reactors. Several of the corresponding cross sections in the fast and epithermal range are included in the Nuclear Energy Agency's High Priority Nuclear Data Request List (e.g., $^{206,207}\text{Pb}(n,n')$, $^{238}\text{U}(n,n')$, $^{238,240,241,242}\text{Pu}(n,f)$, $^{239,241}\text{Pu}(n,\gamma)$). Future development of the VENUS-F pile oscillator aims to reduce the transition time to 2 s, oscillate heated samples for Doppler effect measurements, and include new detectors with various deposits for local effect measurements. The latter requires a dedicated design as the expected magnitude of local perturbations lies at the edge of detectability [10]. Two options for the local detector design are being considered: surrounding an oscillation channel with multiple ^{235}U and ^{238}U fission chambers or surrounding a local detector with an oscillating sample (i.e. oscillating the sample that has a hollow cylinder shape and the detector inserted inside the hole, or the sample made of plates/pins assembled to surround the detector).

Oscillation measurements relative to reference samples are also under consideration at VENUS-F. Suitable reference materials must have well known cross section for all dominant reaction channels in the fast energy range. Elements that satisfy these conditions are hydrogen ($\text{H}(n,\text{el})$ is standard up to 20 MeV), lithium ($^6\text{Li}(n,t)$ is standard up to 1 MeV), boron ($^{10}\text{B}(n,\alpha)$ is standard up to 1 MeV), graphite ($^{\text{nat}}\text{C}(n,\text{el})$ is standard between 1 keV and 1.8 MeV), gold ($^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)$ is standard between 0.2 and 2.5 MeV), uranium ($^{235}\text{U}(n,f)$ is standard above 150 keV (though, capture is not standard), $^{238}\text{U}(n,f)$ is standard above 2 MeV and $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ is standard between 150 eV and 2.2 MeV).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Pile oscillation remains an ideal method for small reactivity worth measurements and reactor transfer function studies. Detector strategy and signal interpretation depend on the neutron spectrum used. Time-domain inverse kinetics analysis and frequency-domain Fourier transform analysis are complementary. Challenges in modelling are expected to be overcome using exact perturbation methods. Hybrid (local + global) detection systems can extend pile oscillation beyond simple reactivity worth measurements toward disentangling reaction channels. The new VENUS-F oscillator is a flexible, versatile device providing variable spectrum, multiple experimental locations, and sample specific oscillation assemblies. The initial version was validated by a consistent detector response and 0.03 pcm experimental uncertainty in open loop.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. P. Wigner. "Use of the Pile Oscillator for the Measurement of Pile Constants." *Chicago Metallurgical Laboratory Report CP-2553* (1945). Reprinted in "The Collected Works of Eugene Paul Wigner", Vol. A/5, Springer (1992).

- [2] B. Geslot, A. Gruel, P. Walczak, P. Leconte, P. Blaise. "A hybrid pile oscillator experiment in the Minerve reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **108**, 268–276 (2017).
- [3] W C. Redman. "Pile Oscillator Determination of Capture To Fission Ratio." *ANL report TID-17738; RED-EPM-102* (1962).
- [4] R.B Tattersall et al. "Pile oscillator measurements of resonance absorption integrals." *Journal of Nuclear Energy. Part A. Reactor Science*, **12**, p. 32-46 (1960).
- [5] S. Hübner et al. "Experimental Determination of the Zero Power Transfer Function of the AKR-2 Reactor." *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2020*. Cambridge, UK, (2020).
- [6] W. K. Foell. "Small-sample reactivity measurements in nuclear reactors." *ANS* (1972).
- [7] F. Di Croce et al. "Oscillation experiments at the VENUS-F fast reactor: measurement of a B₄C reference sample." Manuscript accepted to IEEE, 2025.
- [8] F. Di Croce et al. "Oscillation experiment design at the VENUS-F fast reactor," *EPJ Web of Conferences*, vol. 338, p. 04025, 11 2025.
- [9] F. Di Croce et al. "Small Sample Reactivity Worth Calculation: Comparison of Serpent2 and TRIPOLI4 Perturbation Techniques." pp. 1156–1165. American Nuclear Society (2025).
- [10] F. Di Croce et al. "Design of a PuO₂ oscillation experiment at the VENUS-F fast reactor." In *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2026*. Turin, Italy (19-23 April 2026).
- [11] B. Geslot, A. Gruel, S. Bréaud, P. Leconte, P. Blaise. "Innovative hybrid pile oscillator technique in the Minerve reactor: open loop vs. closed loop." *EPJ* **170** (2018) 04009.
- [12] B. Baker, G. Imel. "Equivalency of Open Loop and Closed Loop Reactivity Measurement Techniques." *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2014*, Kyoto, Japan (2014).
- [13] D. Coll Segarra, G.R. Imel. "The oscillator technique for cross-section measurements in a sub-critical system." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **167** (2022) 108838.
- [14] T. Ligonnet et al. "Design of an Open-Loop Pile-Oscillation Program in the CROCUS Reactor." *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, (2024) DOI 10.1109/TNS.2024.3371183.
- [15] T. Ligonnet et al. "Pile-oscillation results for stainless steel with local and 3D global measurements." *EPJ Web of Conferences* **338**, 04004 (2025).
- [16] Y. Jiang et al. "PISTIL, a reactivity modulation device to probe the transfer function of the nuclear reactor CROCUS." *EPJ Web of Conferences* **253**, 04007 (2021).
- [17] T. Ligonnet et al. "POLLEN: A Pile-Oscillator for the BLOOM Experimental Program." *EPJ Web of Conferences* **288**, 04018 (2023).
- [18] F. Grimaldi et al. "The CoRREx neutron spectrum filtering campaign at VENUS-F for calculation-to-experiment discrepancy interpretation." *Annals of Nucl. En.*, **219**, p. 111425 (2025).
- [19] C.G. Fairclough. "Mesure de la duree moyenne de vie des neutrons dans le reacteur BR.1." SCK CEN report R.1382 (1957).
- [20] G. Truchet, P. Leconte. "Small sample reactivity worths calculation exact perturbation theory and Monte Carlo transport." M&C2019, Aug 2019, Portland, United States. hal-02411094.
- [21] S. Bednyakov et al. The BFS complex – a unique facility to justify the neutronic parameters of the new generation fast reactor cores, *Nuclear Energy and Technology* **8** (2022) 97–105.
- [22] K. Dietze et al. "Integral Test of Neutron Data and Comparison of Codes by Re-analysis of the SEG and STEK Experiments." *JEFF / DOC – 861* (2001).
- [23] S. van der Marck, A. Koning. "STEK: A potential fast spectrum benchmark for fission product cross sections." *Front. Energy Res.* **11**:1085857 (2023).
- [24] P. Leconte et al. "Validation of actinide nuclear data based on reactivity worth experiments in a MOX-LWR spectrum." *Annals of Nuclear Energy* **139** (2020) 107251.
- [25] R. M. Lell. "ZPPR-15 Small Reactivity Worth Experiments." ANL-VTR-53 (2020).
- [26] IAEA. "Critical Experiments and Reactor Physics Calculations for Low Enriched High Temperature Gas Cooled Reactors." IAEA-TECDOC-1249, Vienna, Austria, 2001.
- [27] C. Kostelac. "ER-579 Pile Oscillator Experiments at NCERC." *Ann. NCSP Tech. Prog. Rev.* (2024)
- [28] A. Knospe et al. "Development of the pile oscillation method for the determination of integral cross section data at the AKR-2 training and research reactor." *EPJ WoC* **338**, 04030 (2025).
- [29] G. Truchet, P. Leconte. "Small sample reactivity worths calculation exact perturbation theory and Monte Carlo transport." M&C2019, Aug 2019, Portland, United States. (hal-02411094)